
Research

The Influence Of Social Media Marketing And E-Service Quality On Brand Loyalty Through Customer Satisfaction As A Mediating Variable (A Study On Level Up Consumers By PT Telkom Indonesia)

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Abstract: The development of information and communication technology has transformed the scope of business and marketing, especially through social media as a primary marketing tool. Social media marketing allows companies to reach consumers effectively at a lower cost compared to traditional methods. Along with that, e-service quality, which includes ease, reliability, efficiency, and service security, becomes an important aspect in creating a positive customer experience. However, Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia, as a company operating in the digital sector, is experiencing a decrease in the number of consumers, indicated by the engagement rate on social media and a decline in customer service as seen from the decrease in website visitors. Both factors play a significant role in enhancing customer satisfaction, which drives brand loyalty. This research aims to determine the influence between social media marketing (X1) and e-service quality (X2) on brand loyalty (Y) through customer satisfaction (Z) as the mediating variable. The type of this research is explanatory research, with a non-probability sampling technique applied to 94 sample respondents who are consumers of Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia using the purposive sampling method. The data analysis technique uses SEM-PLS and the data analysis tool SmartPLS 4.0. The results of the coefficient testing from the SEM analysis show that: (H1) accepted; (H2) accepted; (H3) rejected; (H4) rejected; (H5) accepted; (H6) rejected; (H7) accepted. Through this research, it is expected to provide strategic recommendations for Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia in enhancing customer satisfaction and loyalty, while simultaneously strengthening competitiveness in the digital market.

Keywords: Social Media Marketing, E-Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, Brand Loyalty

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Introduction

Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia is currently facing challenges that are affecting their business growth. Based on Table 1, Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia recorded a total of 1,450 consumers from 2020-2024. Although the consumers of Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia experienced the highest increase of 100% in 2022, there was also the highest decrease of 60% in 2024. This indicates that in 2024, Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia has issues related to the number of consumers.

Table 1. Consumer of Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia 2020 - 2024

Year	Consumer Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia	Percentage Increase Each Year
2020	150	-
2021	200	33%
2022	400	100%
2023	500	25%
2024	200	-60%
Total	1450	-

(Source: Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia, 2024)

Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia tries to increase its consumer base every year, one of which is through social media promotion. Social media is one form of promotion that is useful in creating awareness, recognition, recall, and action towards a brand, product, business, individual, or group, both directly and indirectly (Santoso et al., 2017). The social media platforms used by Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia.

Table 2. Sosial media of Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia

Instagram	Tiktok	LinkedIn
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post: 305 • Followers: 24,5K • Following: 8 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Followers: 2.376 • Following: 2 • Like: 60,5K 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Followers: >2K

(Source: Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia, 2024)

Social media measurement is not only based on the number of followers of each account but can also be done through measuring the engagement rate. Engagement rate is a metric used in social media marketing to measure the performance of content on social media platforms. The engagement rate graph for Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia for the years 2023 and 2024.

Figure 1. Social Media Graphics of Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia

(Source: Level Up by PT. Telkom Indonesia, 2024)

In line with table 1, which states that Level Up consumers in 2024 experienced a decrease of 60% from 2023. It can be seen in figure 1, Level Up's social media marketing in 2024 experienced a significant difference compared to 2023. The results indicate that the Instagram engagement rate has an impact on Level Up's consumers.

Besides the issues with social media marketing, there are also problems with e-service quality. Based on interviews with 3 Level Up consumers conducted by the researcher, they believe that sometimes WhatsApp Business, as a customer service platform, does not respond quickly to every inquiry. The delivery of Level Up's products/services also still experiences some delays, both through email and offline shipping services. The result is evidenced in the traffic analysis report from semrush.com in the following image.

Figure 2. Website Traffic Analysis of Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia

(Source: Semrush, 2024)

In addition to the WhatsApp Business issue, Level Up is also facing problems with its official website, level-up.id. Based on the traffic analysis in figure 2 above, Level Up experienced a decrease in the number of visits by 51.55%. This indicates that there has been a decline in customer satisfaction, resulting in a decrease in Level Up's customers in 2024. The limitation of human resources in responding to demands in real-time and the variation in the complexity of customer requests are issues that need to be addressed to improve e-service quality.

Consumer loyalty is the key to long-term success for every company. When customers are satisfied with the products or services they receive, they tend to remain loyal and continue to choose that brand over competitors. Customer satisfaction creates a strong emotional bond between them and the brand, encouraging them to make repeat purchases and even recommend the brand to friends and family. If we look at the table, it shows that consumer satisfaction has not yet reached its maximum due to a continued decline. This is contrary to the development of social media and service quality, which should be able to influence loyalty (Usman et al., 2021).

Research Questions and Objectives

1. To determine the influence of social media marketing on customer satisfaction
2. To determine the influence of e-service quality on customer satisfaction
3. To determine the influence of social media marketing on brand loyalty
4. To determine the influence of e-service quality on brand loyalty
5. To determine the influence of customer satisfaction on brand loyalty
6. To determine the influence of social media marketing on brand loyalty through customer satisfaction as a mediating variable
7. To determine the effect of e-service quality on brand loyalty through customer satisfaction as a mediating variable

Literatur Review

Consumen Behavior

According to Setiadi (2019), consumer behavior is a series of actual actions taken by individuals or groups of individuals, such as organizations, influenced by external and internal factors. According to Ariyanti et al. (2019), consumer behavior refers to the actions taken by consumers in decision-making based on their existing desires. According to Kotler et al

(2008) , consumer behavior is a field of research that studies how individuals, groups, and organizations make choices, make purchases, use, and dispose of products, services, ideas, or experiences to meet their needs and desires.

Social Media Marketing

Gunelius (2011) states that social media marketing is a form of marketing carried out either directly or indirectly to create awareness or actions towards a product, brand, or service using internet tools. According to Bernecker & Beilharz (2011), social media marketing is a marketing activity implemented within the social media environment. According to Godey et al. (2016), social media marketing is measured based on four main dimensions: (1) Entertainment, (2) Interaction, (3) Trendiness, and (4) Customization.

E-Service Quality

Parasuraman et al. (2005) explain that e-service quality encompasses how well a website or application can provide shopping, purchasing, and delivery facilities online with efficiency and effectiveness. Chase & Aquilano (2005) explain that e-service quality is a form of service quality that has been adapted to the internet medium, allowing interaction between sellers and buyers on a larger scale, enhancing the effectiveness and efficiency of shopping activities. According to Parasuraman et al. (2005), the core dimensions of the e-service quality process for measuring service quality consist of: (1) Efficiency, (2) Fulfillment, (3) System Availability, and (4) Privacy.

Customer Satisfaction

Zeithaml & Bitner (2003) explain that customer satisfaction is the evaluation of products or services by customers in relation to the extent to which those products or services meet their needs and expectations. According to Hansemark & Albinsson (2004), customer satisfaction overall reflects the attitude towards the service provider or the emotional reaction to the difference between expectations and the reality received. According to Wilkie & William (1994), there are 4 elements in consumer satisfaction: (1) Expectations, (2) Performance, (3) Comparison, and (4) Confirmation/ disconfirmation.

Brand Loyalty

Mowen & Minor (2002) Brand loyalty refers to the extent to which a consumer shows a positive attitude towards a brand, has a commitment to that brand, and has the intention to continue purchasing it in the future. According to Nagar (2009), brand loyalty is reflected in the consistent purchasing patterns of a particular brand over time, as well as the positive attitude towards that brand. According to Ganesh et al. (2000), there are 5 indicators of brand loyalty, namely: (1) Repeat purchase intention, (2) Self-stated retention, (3) Price insensitivity, (4) Resistance to counter persuasion, (5) Likelihood of spreading positive word of mouth.

Figure 3. Hypothesis Diagram

- H1: The Significant influence of social media marketing (X1) on customer satisfaction (Z)
- H2: The significant influence between e-service quality (X2) and customer satisfaction (Z)
- H3: The influence of social media marketing (X1) on brand loyalty (Y)
- H4: The influence of e-service quality (X2) on brand loyalty (Y)
- H5: The influence between customer satisfaction (Z) and brand loyalty (Y)
- H6: The influence between social media marketing (X1) on brand loyalty through customer satisfaction (Z) as mediation.
- H7: The influence between e-service quality (X2) on brand loyalty (Y) through customer satisfaction (Z) as mediation.

Research Methodology

The research uses an explanatory research type because it explains the cause-and-effect relationship between variables by testing hypotheses with quantitative research methods. The population of this research is all consumers of Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia, totaling 1450 consumers from within Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia. The sample in this study consists of 94 respondents based on Slovin's formula, using a non-probability sampling technique with a purposive sampling method. The criteria for the respondents in this study are

1. At least 17 years old
2. Internal consumers of PT Telkom Indonesia
3. Using Level Up products/services by PT Telkom Indonesia more than 2 times

Data Analysis

Based on the research that has been conducted, the independent variables, social media marketing and e-service quality, affect the dependent variable brand loyalty through customer satisfaction as a mediating variable.

Convergent Validity

Figure 4. Outer Loading

(Source: Primary data processed, 2024)

Based on figure 4, the validity test results from 28 indicators show that 18 indicators are considered significant with a value > 0.7, while the other 10 indicators are not significant because they have a value < 0.7. Therefore, the 10 insignificant indicators must be discarded. Here are the results of the outer model on the valid items.

Table 3. Outer Loading

	Brand Loyalty	Customer Satisfaction	E-Service Quality	Social Media Marketing
BL1	0.831			
BL2	0.859			
BL3	0.801			
BL4	0.854			
BL5	0.713			
CS1		0.796		
CS2		0.811		
CS3		0.835		
CS4		0.759		
ESQ1			0.740	
ESQ2			0.803	
ESQ3			0.762	
ESQ4			0.784	
ESQ5			0.810	
SMM1				0.759
SMM2				0.800
SMM3				0.787
SMM4				0.763

Source: Primary data processed (2024)

Convergent Validity can be determined from the loading factor value of the indicator or construct and the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) score. According to Hair et al. (2022), an indicator is said to have good reliability if the factor loading value > 0.70, composite reliability > 0.7, and AVE score > 0.5.

Table 4 AVE (Average Variance Extracted)

	AVE (Average Variance Extracted)
Social Media Marketing (X1)	0.662
E Service Quality (X2)	0.641
Customer Satisfaction (Z)	0.609
Brand Loyalty (Y)	0.605

Source: Primary data processed (2024)

Based on table 4, the calculation of the AVE value for each variable exceed 0.5, which means the data can be considered valid.

Discriminant Validity

Discriminant Validity is a test to determine the AVE value based on the Fornell-Lacker Criterion and Cross Loading. Discriminant Validity is said to be fulfilled if the correlation value between indicators on the latent variable is higher than the correlation with other variables.

Table 5. Fornell-Lacker Criterion

	Brand Loyalty	Customer Satisfaction	E Service Quality	Social Media Marketing
Brand Loyalty	0.813			
Customer Satisfaction	0.721	0.800		
E Service Quality	0.639	0.820	0.780	
Social Media Marketing	0.574	0.697	0.719	0.778

Source: Primary data processed (2024)

Discriminant validity is determined by the ratio of the square root of AVE to the construct correlation or can be determined from cross loading and from the indicators with their constructs. This can be seen in the following table:

Table 6. Cross Loading

	Brand Loyalty	Customer Satisfaction	E-Service Quality	Social Media Marketing
BL1	0.831	0.534	0.498	0.423
BL2	0.859	0.613	0.512	0.499
BL3	0.801	0.500	0.469	0.303
BL4	0.854	0.537	0.479	0.420
BL5	0.713	0.687	0.596	0.609
CS1	0.602	0.796	0.688	0.596
CS2	0.555	0.811	0.627	0.601
CS3	0.669	0.835	0.671	0.483
CS4	0.469	0.759	0.637	0.557
ESQ1	0.507	0.634	0.740	0.608
ESQ2	0.485	0.590	0.803	0.622
ESQ3	0.416	0.551	0.762	0.428
ESQ4	0.493	0.641	0.784	0.544
ESQ5	0.572	0.753	0.810	0.588
SMM2	0.406	0.505	0.503	0.759
SMM3	0.450	0.567	0.553	0.800
SMM4	0.462	0.553	0.563	0.787

Source: Primary data processed (2024)

Cross loading is the maximum loading relationship on one construct compared to other constructs. Based on table 3.5, the loading score of BL1 is 0.831, which is considered the highest compared to the correlation of BL1 with other variables, such as the correlation with customer satisfaction at 0.534, then the e-service quality variable at 0.498, and the social media marketing variable at 0.423. The same results are found in other constructs with each indicator. Discriminant validity is considered good based on the rule of thumb if the cross-loading score > 0.7 (Henseler, 2015). Therefore, the conclusion of table 3.4 indicates that the data is good and can proceed to the next stage.

Reliability Test

Reliability testing on a model with reflective indicators can be assessed using two techniques, namely by considering the values of Cronbach’s alpha and composite reliability.

Table 7. Cronbach’s Alpha and Composite Reliability

	Cronbach’s Alpha	Composite Reliability
Social Media Marketing (X1)	0.872	0.875
E Service Quality (X2)	0.813	0.816
Customer Satisfaction (Z)	0.840	0.845
Brand Loyalty (Y)	0.782	0.783

Source: Primary data processed (2024)

Based on Table 7, the minimum Cronbach's alpha value is for the social media marketing variable with a value of 0.813, and the maximum value is for the brand loyalty variable with a value of 0.872. The output composite reliability scores demonstrate satisfactory scores for each variable, exceeding 0.70.

R-Square

The inner model aims to determine the R-square used as the goodness-of-fit measure (Ghozali & Latan, 2015). R-square aims to assess how much the endogenous construct can be explained by the exogenous construct. The expected value of the coefficient of determination (R-square) is between 0 and 1.

Table 8. R-Square

	R-square
Brand Loyalty	0.533
Customer Satisfaction	0.696

Source: Primary data processed (2024)

According to Chin & Marcoulides (1998), the R-Square value is considered strong if it is more than 0.67, moderate if it is between 0.33 and 0.67, and weak if it is more than 0.19 but less than 0.33. Based on table 3.15, it is known that the influence of social media marketing and e-service quality variables on brand loyalty is 0.533, which means it has a moderate influence. Meanwhile, the influence of social media marketing and e-service quality variables on customer satisfaction is 0.692, which means it has a strong impact.

Path Coefficient

Hypothesis testing can be determined by examining the path parameter in the path coefficient and the significance level of the T-Statistic. The results of the hypothesis test are used to prove the correlation between the variables that are hypothesized. The path coefficient parameter will explain the negative or positive correlation of the variable used in the hypothesis. If the p-value < 0.05, then the hypothesis is accepted.

Figure 5. Path Coefficient

(Source: Primary data processed, 2024)

Hypothesis testing was conducted using the bootstrapping technique with 5000 subsamples Ong Chuan Huat et al. (2018). The significance test of the path coefficient is conducted by dividing the t-statistic score by the t-table score at the 5% significance level, which is equal to 1.96. The influential path coefficient can be said to be significant if the t-statistic score exceeds the t-table score > 1.96. (Hair et al., 2022)

Result and Discussion

After conducting experiments to test the influence on each variable used in this study, it can be concluded that the results from the data processing are as follows:

Table 9. Data Processing Results H1-H7

	Path Coefficient	T-Statistic	P-Value	Noted
Direct Effect				
(X1) -> (Z)	0.221	2.007	0.045	H1 Accepted
(X2) -> (Z)	0.661	7.675	0.000	H2 Accepted
(X1) -> (Y)	0.111	0.982	0.326	H3 Rejected
(X2) -> (Y)	0.096	0.555	0.579	H4 Rejected
(Z) -> (Y)	0.565	3.851	0.000	H5 Accepted
Indirect Effect				
(X1) -> (Z) -> (Y)	0.125	1.733	0.083	H6 Rejected
(X3) -> (Z) -> (Y)	0.374	3.353	0.001	H7 Accepted

Source: Primary data processed (2024)

Noted:

- X1: Social Media Marketing Y : Brand Loyalty
- X2: E-Service Quality Z : Customer Satisfaction

Figure 6. Final Research Diagram

(Source: Primary data processed, 2024)

The results of the H1 test show a path coefficient value of 0.221 (positive), a t-statistic value of 2.007 (< 1.96), and a p-value of 0.045 (< 0.05). Therefore, it can be said that social media marketing has a significant influence on customer satisfaction, which means that **hypothesis 1 is accepted**. This research is in line with studies conducted by Usman et al. (2021), Frans et al. (2023), and Mukaromah & Untoro (2006), which state that social media marketing has a significant impact on customer satisfaction.

The results of the H2 test show a path coefficient value of 0.661 (positive), a t-statistic value of 7.675 (> 0.196), and a p-value of 0.00 (< 0.05). Therefore, it can be said that e-service quality has a positive and significant impact on customer satisfaction, which means **hypothesis 2 is accepted**. This research is in line with studies conducted by Priatmojo et al., (2023), Zuliestiana & Setiawan (2022), and Raras & Sakti (2021) which state that e-service quality has a significant impact on customer satisfaction.

The results of testing H3 show a path coefficient value of 0.111 (positive), a t-statistic value of 0.982 (> 1.96), and a p-value of 0.326 (> 0.05). Therefore, it can be said that social media marketing has a positive but insignificant effect on brand loyalty, which means **hypothesis 3 is rejected**. This study is not in line with the research conducted by Erdoğan & Çiçek (2012), Haudi et al. (2022), and Zulfa et al. (2023) which state that social media marketing has a significant influence on brand loyalty. And according to the research by Halim & Sutanto (2021), it proves a negative influence between social media marketing and brand loyalty.

The results of testing H4 show a path coefficient value of 0.096 (positive), a t-statistic value of 0.555 (> 1.96), and a p-value of 0.579 (< 0.05). It can be said that e-service quality has an insignificant effect on brand loyalty, which means that **hypothesis 4 is rejected**. This study is in line with the research conducted by Sulistio & Bastaman (2023), and Waruwu & Sahir (2022), which states that e-service quality does not have a significant impact on e-loyalty. However, according to Cahyarani & Astuti (2022), E-Service Quality has a significant influence on e-loyalty.

The results of the H5 test show a path coefficient value of 0.565 (positive), a t-statistic value of 3.851 (> 1.96), and a p-value of 0.000 (< 0.05). Therefore, it can be said that customer satisfaction has a significant impact on brand loyalty, which means that **hypothesis 5 is accepted**. This research is in line with studies conducted by Firmansyah et al. (2023), Utami et al. (2023), and Ahmed et al. (2014), which state that customer satisfaction has a significant impact on brand loyalty.

The results of testing H6 show a path coefficient value of 0.125 (positive), a t-statistic value of 1.733 (< 1.96), and a p-value of 0.083 (> 0.05). Therefore, it can be said that the mediating relationship of social media marketing on brand loyalty through customer satisfaction is no mediation because after including customer satisfaction, it does not have a significant influence, which means **hypothesis 6 is rejected**. This research is not in line with the studies conducted by Usman et al. (2021) and Haudi et al. (2022) which state that social media marketing has a significant impact on brand loyalty and customer satisfaction.

The results of the H7 test show a path coefficient value of 0.374 (positive), a t-statistic value of 3.353 (> 1.96), and a p-value of 0.001 (< 0.05). Therefore, it can be said that the mediation relationship of e-service quality on brand loyalty through customer satisfaction is partial mediation because after including customer satisfaction, it can have a significant impact, which means **hypothesis 7 is accepted**. These results indicate that Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia consumers are perceived to have good service quality, thereby increasing consumer satisfaction as they experience what they desire, ultimately encouraging consumer loyalty towards the products/services of Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Conclusion

Based on the research results above regarding the influence of social media marketing and e-service quality on brand loyalty through customer satisfaction as a mediating variable among Level Up consumers by PT Telkom Indonesia:

1. Social media marketing has a significant impact on customer satisfaction. This is because Level Up's social media successfully attracts users' attention through interactive content, thereby impacting overall customer satisfaction.
2. E-Service Quality has a significant impact on customer satisfaction. This result is due to users feeling that the e-service quality of Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia is considered very good and meets user expectations.

3. Social media marketing has an insignificant influence on brand loyalty. This result is due to customers feeling that Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia has not yet utilized social media as a means to support customers after sales through social media.
4. E-Service Quality has an insignificant effect on brand loyalty. This is because certain expectations from Level Up consumers can influence the quality of electronic services on consumer loyalty. Level Up consumers by PT Telkom Indonesia still tend to compare many service options with similar quality, so there are still consumers who want to switch to competitors.
5. Customer satisfaction has a significant impact on brand loyalty. This result is due to users feeling that effective complaint handling can increase satisfaction and make customers feel more attached.
6. Social media marketing has an insignificant effect on brand loyalty through customer satisfaction as a mediating variable. This result is due to users feeling that Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia has not yet focused on creating content related to post-purchase, so consumers who have used Level Up's products/services are not yet fully loyal.
7. E-service quality has a significant impact on brand loyalty through customer satisfaction as a mediating variable. This result is because users feel that Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia has good service quality, which increases consumer satisfaction as they experience what they desire, ultimately encouraging consumer loyalty towards the products/services of Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia.

Recommendation

1. On the social media marketing variable, the suggestion that can be given is that Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia can focus more on content personalization, such as offering products/services tailored to user preferences based on their behavior data on social media.
2. On the e-service quality variable, the suggestion that can be given is that Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia can add an intuitive search feature or relevant tags. Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia can provide clear descriptions of products/services for all products/services so that users are informed. Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia can also enhance communication during the delivery process, such as providing real-time delivery status notifications.
3. On the Customer Satisfaction variable, the suggestion that can be given is that Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia is expected to focus more on improving service quality and personalizing interactions to continuously enhance customer satisfaction.
4. On the Brand Loyalty variable, the suggestion that can be given is that Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia is expected to create a loyalty program that offers special benefits for loyal customers, providing exclusive access, discounts, or attractive rewards for customers. Level Up by PT Telkom Indonesia can also utilize storytelling, testimonials, and case studies from real users that demonstrate positive experiences.
5. Further research is expected to examine the relationship between social media marketing and e-service quality with brand loyalty, by increasing the sample size or number of respondents, changing the research object to other service companies, and adding other variables not included in this study, such as other research variables that can influence customer satisfaction and brand loyalty. This research has limitations because it is only applied to one brand, and it is hoped to obtain broader information by conducting research on several brands and to reduce bias in the study. The results obtained, whether they are the same or if there are other factors influencing them.

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References

- [1] Ahmed, Z., Rizwan, M., Ahmad, M., & Haq, M. (2014). Effect of brand trust and customer satisfaction on brand loyalty in Bahawalpur. *Journal of Sociological Research*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.5296/jsr.v5i1.6568>
- [2] Amanda Zuliestiana, D., & Nursalma Setiawan, A. (2022). Pengaruh E-Service Quality Terhadap E-Customer Satisfaction Dan Dampaknya Terhadap E-Customer Loyalty Pada Pengguna Aplikasi Bca Mobile. 6(2).
- [3] Ariyanti, & Aditya Gusrah Arsyalan. (2019). Pengaruh Electronic Word Of Mouth (Ewom) Terhadap The Impact Of Electronic Word Of Mouth On Shopee's Purchasing Decision In Bandung.
- [4] Bernecker, M., & Beilharz, F. (2011). *Social Media Marketing*. Johanna Verlag.
- [5] Cahyarani, B., & Astuti, R. T. (2022). Analisis Pengaruh E-Customer Relationship Management (E-Crm) Dan E-Service Quality Terhadap E-Loyalty Dengan E-Wom Sebagai Variabel Intervening (Studi pada Pengguna Aplikasi MAPCLUB di Kota Semarang). *Diponegoro Journal Of Management*, 11(3). <http://ejournal-s1.undip.ac.id/index.php/dbr>
- [6] Chase, R., & Aquilano, N. (2005). *Operations Management for Competitive Advantage*.
- [7] Chin, W., & Marcoulides, G. (1998). The Partial Least Squares Approach to Structural Equation Modeling. *Modern Methods for Business Research*, 8.
- [8] Dainy Sulistio, W., & Bastaman, A. (2023). Enrichment: Journal of Management The effects of e-trust, e-service quality and e-wom to e-loyalty with e-satisfaction as an intervening variables of jenius app users in Jakarta. In *Enrichment: Journal of Management (Vol. 12, Issue 6)*.
- [9] Erdoğan, İ. E., & Çiçek, M. (2012). The Impact of Social Media Marketing on Brand Loyalty. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 58, 1353–1360. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.09.1119>
- [10] Firmansyah, F., Sugiat, M. A., & Yunita, I. (2023). The Impact Of Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, And Trust On Customer Loyalty Among Brilink Agents In North Sumatra. In *International Journal of Science*. <http://ijstm.inarah.co.id>
- [11] Frans Sudirjo, I Nyoman Tri Sutaguna, Rina Sovianti, Arief Yanto Rukmana, & PA. Andiena nindya putri. (2023). Social Media Marketing's Effect On Customer Satisfaction. *International Journal of Economics and Management Research*, 2(2), 109–118. <https://doi.org/10.55606/ijemr.v2i2.100>
- [12] Ganesh, Jaishankar, Mark J. Arnold, & Kristy E. Reynolds. (2000). Understanding The Customer Base of Services Providers: An Examination of The Differences Between Switchers and Stayers. *Journal of Marketing*, 65–87.
- [13] Ghozali, & Latan. (2015). *Partial least squares konsep, teknik dan aplikasi menggunakan program SmartPLS 3.0 untuk penelitian empiris (2nd ed.)*. Semarang Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- [14] Godey, B., Manthiou, A., Pederzoli, D., Rokka, J., Aiello, G., Donvito, R., & Singh, R. (2016). Social media marketing efforts of luxury brands: Influence on brand equity and consumer behavior. *Journal of Business Research*, 69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2016.04.181>
- [15] Gunelius. (2011). *30-Minute Social Media Marketing*. McGraw-Hill Companies.
- [16] Hair, J., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C., & Sarstedt, M. (2022). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*.

- [17] Halim, C. M., & Sutanto, J. E. (2021). The Relevance Of Price, Lifestyle, And Social Media Towards Purchase Decisions Of Motato Product. *Business and Accounting Research (IJEBAR) Peer Reviewed-International Journal*, 5. <https://jurnal.stie-aas.ac.id/index.php/IJEBAR>
- [18] Hansemark, O., & Albinsson, M. (2004). Customer satisfaction and retention: The experiences of individual employees. *Managing Service Quality*, 14, 40–57. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09604520410513668>
- [19] Haudi, Handayani, W., Musnaini, Suyoto, Y. T., Prasetyo, T., Pital-Oka, E., Wijoyo, H., Yonata, H., Koho, I. R., & Cahyono, Y. (2022). The effect of social media marketing on brand trust, brand equity and brand loyalty. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 6(3), 961–972. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.ijdns.2022.1.015>
- [20] John C. Mowen, & Michael Minor. (2002). *Perilaku konsumen*. Jakarta Erlangga.
- [21] Kotler, P., & Gary Armstrong. (2008). *Prinsip-prinsip Pemasaran* (Adi Maulana, Devri Barnadi, & Wibi Hardani, Eds.; 12th ed.). Erlangga.
- [22] Mukaromah, R., & Untoro, W. (2006). Pengaruh Social Media Marketing Activities, Programme Membership, Celebrity Endorsment, Brand Image Dan Customer Satisfaction Dan Customer Loyalty Sebagai Variabel Mediasi Pada Pengunjung Kedai Kopi Cold N Brew Di Solo.
- [23] Nagar, K. (2009). Evaluating the Effect of Consumer Sales Promotions on Brand Loyal and Brand Switching Segments. *Vision: The Journal of Business Perspective*, 13, 35–48. <https://doi.org/10.1177/097226290901300404>
- [24] Ong Chuan Huat, D., Lee, H., & Ramayah, T. (2018). Impact of brand experience on loyalty. *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19368623.2018.1445055>
- [25] Parasuraman, A. P., Zeithaml, V., & Malhotra, A. (2005). E-S-Qual: A Multiple-Item Scale for Assessing Electronic Service Quality. *Journal of Service Research*, 7, 213–233. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094670504271156>
- [26] Priatmojo, A. A., Welsa, H., Agus,), & Cahya, D. (2023). The Effect Of Experiential Marketing And E-Service Quality On Customer Satisfaction With Brand Image As An Intervening Variable (Case Study on Consumers Dazzle Gejayan). *Jurnal Terapan Manajemen Dan Bisnis*, 9, 61–75.
- [27] Raras, A., & Sakti, T. (2021). Analysis of the Effect of E-Service Quality on Hospital Customer Satisfaction (Study of E-Service Quality Hospitals in West Java, Indonesia). <https://www.bps.go.id/>.
- [28] Santoso, A. P., Baihaqi, I., & Persada, S. F. (2017). Pengaruh Konten Post Instagram terhadap Online Engagement: Studi Kasus pada Lima Merek Pakaian Wanita. *Jurnal Teknik ITS*, 6(1), 217–221.
- [28] Semrush. (2024). SEMrush: Top SEO Tool.
- [29] Setiadi, N. J. (2019). *Perilaku Konsumen: Perspektif Kontemporer pada Motif, Tujuan, dan Keinginan Konsumen* (Cetakan ketujuh, Ed.; Revisi).
- [30] Usman, D., Yulianto, E., & Sunarti. (2021). Pengaruh Social Media Marketing Terhadap Kesadaran Merek, Citra Merek Dan Kepuasan Konsumen. <https://Profit.Ub.Ac.Id>
- [31] Utami, P., Bernarto, I., Hutabarat, Z., & Harapan, U. P. (2023). The Effect Of Satisfaction And Trust On Member Loyalty Reload byHP under a Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International License (CC BY-NC 4.0). *Jurnal Ekonomi*, 12(01), 2023. <http://ejournal.seaninstitute.or.id/index.php/Ekonomi>
- [32] Waruwu, K. K., & Sahir, S. H. (2022). Pengaruh E-Service Quality dan Brand Image Terhadap E-Loyalty pada Pengguna Aplikasi Shopee. *Journal of Business and Economics Research (JBE)*, 3(3), 335–341. <https://doi.org/10.47065/jbe.v3i3.2298>
- [33] Wilkie, & William L. (1994). *Consumer Behavior* (3rd ed.). John Willey & Sons, Inc.
- [34] Zeithaml, V. A., & Bitner, M. J. (2003). *Services Marketing: Integrating Customer Focus across the Firm* (Irwin McGraw-Hill, Ed.; 3rd Edition).
- [35] Zulfa, A., Vutri, F., Komariah, K., & Mulia, F. (2023). Analysis Of Social Media Marketing And Brand Love On Brand Loyalty Study Of Skintific Product Marketing On Followers Instagram Kawaidollshop Analisis Social Media

Marketing Dan Brand Love Terhadap Loyalty Brand Studi Pemasaran Produk Skintific Pada Followers Instagram Kawaidollshop.

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